

Study of heat losses during charge, discharge and storage period of a LHTES system operating at ultra-high temperatures

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Abstract:

This paper studies the thermal performance of a silicon based latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) system, operating at ultra-high temperatures (>1100 K), during charge, discharge and storage period. During charging, the system stores energy in the form of latent heat. During discharging, the stored energy is released from the vessel bottom and is converted into electricity. Owing to the system's operation at such unprecedented temperatures, there is a high necessity to deal with several technical issues, including high heat losses through the vessel sidewalls. Thus, a validated transient computational fluid dynamics model is applied in ANSYS Fluent v17.0 platform, combining the volume of fluid method with the enthalpy porosity approach, and proper user-defined functions to consider lateral heat losses. Initially, a parametric study is conducted by varying the insulating materials thermal resistance (R) within the range 0.1 - 4.8 $\text{m}^2\text{K}/\text{W}$. Furthermore, different vessel geometries (truncated cone, cylinder) with tapering ratios (TR) –ratio of bottom to upper surface- equal to 0.225 , 0.45 and 1 , and volumes ranging from $4V$ to $V/4$ ($V=8.33\text{e-}04$ m^3) are investigated. During solidification/melting, it is observed that the average heat losses can be an order of magnitude higher for an insulation with $R\approx 0.1$ $\text{m}^2\text{K}/\text{W}$ than that with $R\approx 2$ $\text{m}^2\text{K}/\text{W}$. Another important conclusion drawn is that during discharging the excessive lateral heat losses might cause an undesirable solidification of the PCM near the vessel sidewalls and upper part. Owing to this, there is a high risk of entrapping the molten PCM inside the solid one, and therefore increase the pressure inside the system. Considering the vessel geometry, a moderate effect of the TR on the lateral losses is noticed, especially for insulating materials with $R\approx 2$ $\text{m}^2\text{K}/\text{W}$. Finally, the crucible volume plays an important role on the system losses, especially during storage period that the material should maintain its temperature close to its melting point.

Keywords:

Charge/discharge, Heat losses, Numerical simulation, TES, Ultra-high temperatures.

1. Introduction

During the next decades, solar energy as an abundant renewable energy source will empower the scientific and technical community worldwide to achieve the energy shift from fossil fuels to renewable-based energy production. As a further step, combining thermal energy storage (TES) and solar energy can help eliminate the gap between supply and demand, especially during periods of low solar availability, such as winter and night-time. The basic principle of a TES system is the storage of any kind of energy –waste, solar, thermal- in the form of sensible and/or latent heat, and its further exploitation through a heat sink. Since the whole system operation is based on a full cycle of charge, discharge and storage period, its efficiency is highly dependent on its behaviour during these three periods [1]. Some of the key elements reflecting an effective storage system operation are quick charge/ discharge rates, high storage and power densities and low thermal losses. In this context, an in-depth research is needed to optimize such systems and move towards higher efficiencies.

Among the different TES technologies available today, latent heat TES is considered as the most promising, due to its several advantages, including the high energy density within a given volume and at an almost constant temperature range [2]. The materials utilized in such systems are known as phase change materials (PCMs); the two key characteristics of a PCM that affect significantly the performance of a LHTES system are its melting temperature and its latent heat of fusion. Utilizing metallic PCMs with high melting temperatures and thermal conductivities, such as Si, Al, B or their alloys, can help unlock high energy densities and move towards higher system efficiencies [3] [4]. However, when the TES is used for power generation there is a maximum temperature limit imposed by the intermediate heat transfer fluids (HTF) used in the state-of-the-art systems. Recently Datas et al. [5] have proposed a novel concept of a silicon based LHTES system coupled with a thermionic-photovoltaic converter, which directly converts the stored heat into electricity, without the need of an intermediate HTF. Such a concept has a practical potential of achieving 40-50% efficiency.

Nevertheless, prior to the construction of this novel system, there is a necessity to deal with several technical challenges, arising from its operation at such high temperatures (>1100 K). First, the high heat losses from the LHTES vessel sidewalls, Figure 1, which are difficult to eliminate, unless a proper insulating method is applied. Other challenges include achieving high charge/discharge rates, and maximum power output, which are highly dependent on the vessel design. In [6] it is highlighted that the heat transfer enhancement in the design of the PCM storage tank and elimination of heat losses is a necessity for efficient systems. Supplementary, special design considerations and safety measures, such as release valves to remove gases from the system when the pressure increases [7], are needed in order to efficiently utilize the PCMs in specific applications, such as concentrated solar power (CSP), as the LHTES might crack due to PCM expansion. Therefore, the geometrical configuration of the PCM container and its optimization is of high importance, in order to maximize the efficiency and power output of the system and ensure its safe operation.

Regarding the LHTES investigations, there exist many analytical, experimental and numerical studies evaluating the thermal performance of PCMs, such as paraffin wax, inside various containers of spherical, cylindrical or rectangular shape [8]. However, the vast majority of them are performed for low temperatures, and there is less research for the process performance under ultra-high temperatures. Additionally, most of them have focused on the storage material property and overall system performance enhancement [4] and a few of them study the heat transfer phenomena inside the LHTES design itself. Additionally, as noticed in [1] most the studies do not consider the storage period between the charging and discharging processes, since these studies are mainly focused either on the charge or discharge phase. Finally, excess lateral heat losses, which might lead the PCM to be partially solidified and, therefore, to eliminate maximum power output have been neglected [2].

Thus, the aim of this work is to thoroughly investigate the full cycle of the novel LHTES system, Figure 1, proposed by Datas et al. [5], by taking into account lateral heat losses; this system is studied as part of a P2H2P (power-to-heat-to-power) concept, but can be alternatively implemented into S2H2P (solar-to-heat-to-power) applications. Several vessel geometries, volumes and insulating materials are investigated. This research activity is performed by means of an advanced two-

dimensional (2D) CFD model, which is implemented in ANSYS Fluent platform (v17.1) [9]. The CFD model applied is based on the enthalpy-porosity approach [10] coupled with the Volume of fluid (VOF) model. Compared to state-of-the-art models [11] that are used for studying vessels operating at temperatures above 1100 K with various simplifications, this one incorporates the effect of complex phenomena, as those of natural convection in the PCM liquid phase and volumetric expansion/compression due to PCM solidification/melting process. In this system, the PCM occupies part of the vessel and above it, a non-reacting gas fills the rest of the domain. For a more accurate representation of the gas-PCM and solid-liquid PCM interfaces, a number of in-house user-defined functions (UDFs), are implemented so that a grid adaptive local refinement [12] is applied, both in the PCM-gas and solid-liquid interfaces. This technique is used to enhance the numerical results accuracy and efficiency. To the best of the authors' knowledge, for the first time, such an advanced CFD model is implemented for the simulation and design optimization of a LHTES system operating at such ultra-high temperatures, by taking simultaneously into account thermal losses.

Figure 1. Novel LHTES-TIPV system during a) charge/ discharge and b) TES period.

2. Numerical methodology

The CFD model applied in this work has been previously verified against an analytical model [7], describing the silicon solidification process inside a sealed crucible. In this section, some of the assumptions adopted are briefly presented, whilst a more detailed analysis and equations of the volume of fluid method and enthalpy porosity approach can be found in [7] and [13]:

1. **Transient fluid flow** and heat transfer mechanisms;
2. Solution of an **axisymmetric problem**;
3. Inclusion of **gravity effect**;
4. The flow is considered to be **laminar, due to low Reynolds numbers for the cases studied**;
5. The **molten PCM** is treated as an **incompressible Newtonian fluid**;
6. Both solid and liquid phases of the **PCM** are **homogeneous and isotropic**;
7. The **PCM thermophysical properties, and insulating materials thermal properties** are **dependent on temperature variations**;
8. The **PCM density changes** during its transition from solid to liquid phase and vice versa;
9. The inert gas is treated as a compressible fluid, by solving Tait equation [9];
10. Radiative heat transfer within the vessel is neglected;
11. **Contact thermal resistances** between solid/liquid PCM and walls are considered **negligible**;

12. The crucible walls and insulating layers are modelled as thin walls, by solving an 1D heat conduction equation [9].

2.1. Numerical cases examined

This section presents the different scenarios investigated in the framework of this analysis.

Regarding the vessel insulation, two methods have been tested, Figure 2a. In the first one, only graphite fiber mat- GFM (Case 1A, Table 1) is used. In the second one, GFM is utilized as an inner layer and fumed silica board-FSB as an outer layer (Case 2A-4A, Table 1). Data concerning materials thermal properties are retrieved by [14]. Their values have been calculated by taking into account both thermal conduction and radiation through the insulating materials. The geometry used in this set of cases studied is the inversed truncated cone (ITC) with a tapering ratio TR equal to 0.45 and a reference volume V equal to $8.326e-04 \text{ m}^3$ (Case 1B, Table 2). The cases simulated are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. List of cases studied regarding the container insulating layers effect on system heat losses.

Case	# Layers	b_{GFM} [m]	b_{FSB} [m]	$R_{\text{total},1680}^*$ [$\text{m}^2 \text{K}\cdot\text{W}^{-1}$]	Phase studied
Case 1A	1	0.03	-	0.1179	Charge/ Discharge
Case 2A	2	0.03	0.06	1.88	Charge/ Discharge
Case 3A	2	0.06	0.09	2.88	Discharge
Case 4A	2	0.1	0.15	4.80	Discharge

* Insulating materials thermal resistance at a temperature $T=1680 \text{ K}$.

As concerns the vessel geometry, the following cases have been investigated:

A. During system charge/discharge, Table 2:

- I. Different vessel volumes V (Case 1B), V/2 (Case 2B) and V/4 (Case 3B);
- II. Different vessel tapering ratios [TR=1 (Case 5B-6B), 0.45 (Case 1B), 0.225 (Case 4B)], by keeping the latent heat storage system volume constant equal to V.

Table 2. List of cases studied regarding the container design effect on system performance during charge/ discharge phase.

Case	V [m^3]	A_{em} [m^2]	A_{abs} [m^2]	A_{wall} [m^2]	H [m]	Shape	Phase studied
Case 1B	0.0008326	0.0045	0.01081	0.03456	0.1121	ITC	Charge/ Discharge
Case 2B	0.0004163	0.0045	0.01081	0.01813	0.0560	ITC	Charge/ Discharge
Case 3B	0.0002081	0.0045	0.01081	0.01058	0.0280	ITC	Charge/ Discharge
Case 4B	0.0008326	0.0045	0.02054	0.03130	0.0721	ITC	Charge/ Discharge
Case 5B	0.0008326	0.0045	0.0045	0.0440	0.185	Cylinder	Charge/ Discharge
Case 6B	0.0008326	0.01081	0.01081	0.02839	0.077	Cylinder	Charge/ Discharge

B. During storage period:

I. Different ITC volumes (V, V/2, V/4, 2V and 4V), Table 4. In this set of cases tested (Table 2), insulating method of two layers (Case 2A, Table 1) has been used.

2.2. Geometry and mesh layout

The vessel geometry –volume V and TR ratio equal to 0.45- and discretised domain used during insulating layers parametric study are depicted in Figure 2a and Figure 2b, respectively. The ITC geometry is placed vertically and contains silicon as a PCM. At its bottom, the emitter of the TIPV converter is fixed, coming into direct contact with the molten silicon. During system discharge, the TIPV anode, which comprises a thermionic and a photovoltaic cell, is patched to the system and is irradiated by the emitter, producing electricity. This radiated heat, which is more or less dependent on the emitter temperature $-Q=Q_{\text{em}}(T)$, eq. (1) - causes the PCM solidification. During charge or TES period, the TIPV converter anode is dispatched from the system, insulating materials are placed on

the vessel bottom part and, as a result, the emitter stops radiating heat. Other surfaces in the vessel include lateral and upper walls, designated in this analysis as walls and absorber, respectively.

$$Q_{em} = -(3.17E - 04 * T_{em}^3 - 0.7616 * T_{em}^2 + 6.438E02 * T_{em} - 1.8385E05) \quad (1)$$

Figure 2. a) Cases investigated during the insulating layers parametric study and b) computational domain (purple: emitter surface, green: axis, red: absorber, black: walls).

In Figure 3 are depicted the mesh layouts of the different geometries tested. An adaptive grid local refinement technique of 3 levels [12] is applied through user-defined functions (UDFs) in order to capture the sharp gas-PCM and solid-liquid interfaces without substantial increase of the associated computational cost compared to dense grids of the same minimum resolution. This technique results in a maximum grid size of almost 20,000 quadrilateral cells, in all cases. The refined grid comprises elements of maximum and minimum cell volume equal to $3e-07 \text{ m}^3$ and $1e-11 \text{ m}^3$, respectively.

Figure 3. Mesh layout of the studied geometries: a) Case1B, b) Case4B, c) Case5B and d) Case6B.

2.3. Boundary and operating conditions

Solidification/ melting process

In Table 3 are presented the boundary conditions assigned during the system charge/discharge. More specifically, during discharging, the heat flux at the emitter surface follows the temperature dependent equation (1). The rest of the surfaces (wall, absorber) are insulated, whilst a temperature equal to 300 K is considered at the system exterior surface, assuming that the temperature there tends to homogenize to the ambient one (study of worst case scenario). During system charge, the temperature at the lateral walls, where the heater is placed, is defined equal to $T_{wall}=2000 \text{ K}$. At the rest of the surfaces (emitter, absorber), a temperature equal to 300 K is considered at the system exterior surface.

The PCM-gas thermophysical properties are retrieved from [7]. Its melting and solidification points are equal to 1681 K and 1679 K, respectively. During system discharge, the temperature is initially ($t=0$) set equal to 1680 K at the emitter and equal to 1960 K at the absorber. For the rest of the domain a linear interpolation of these two values is used to patch the temperature profile. The PCM melting process is simulated shortly after its solidification phase. Initially, the solid PCM fills 92 % of the vessel, to avoid any problems due to its expansion after melting. In this phase, the PCM subdomain is patched with a temperature 140 degrees lower than its melting point.

Table 3. CFD problem boundary conditions used during system charge/ discharge phase.

		BC type	Parameters	Units	Values
<i>Solidification</i>	<i>Wall/ Absorber</i>	Wall	T	K	300
			$R_{insulation}$	$m^2 \cdot K \cdot W^{-1}$	Varying, (Table 1)
			b_{vessel}	m	0.01
			k_{vessel}	$W \cdot m^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$	12.5
<i>Emitter</i>	Wall	Q	$W \cdot m^{-2}$	$Q_{em}(T)$, eq. (1)	
<i>Melting</i>	<i>Emitter/ Absorber</i>	Wall	T	K	300
			$R_{insulation}$	$m^2 \cdot K \cdot W^{-1}$	Varying, (Table 1)
	<i>Wall</i>	Wall	T_{wall}	K	2000
			b_{vessel}	m	0.01
			k_{vessel}	$W \cdot m^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$	12.5

Storage period

In order to study and estimate how much time will pass until the vessel loses completely its contained energy in the form of latent heat during storage period the different concepts tested are patched at 2000 K. All the walls (including at the emitter) are insulated following the insulating method presented in Table 1 (Case 2A). Since the storage period lasts more time than charge/discharge phase, more realistic boundary conditions have been imposed at the system outer surface. Therefore, an ambient temperature of 300 K has been considered, whilst both convective and radiative heat losses to the environment are calculated. A value of a convective heat transfer coefficient equal to $20 \text{ W} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$ and external emissivity equal to 0.3 are set to the system exterior surfaces.

3. Results

3.1. Insulating layers effect

In Figure 4, are depicted contours of the silicon melting fraction inside the crucible for the different insulating layers tested. As can be noticed, in all cases a gradual solidification of the PCM occurs from the bottom to the upper region of the vessel, owing to heat release from the emitter. What differentiates each case is the heat losses from the vessel sidewalls and upper part, due to different insulating materials/thicknesses applied, which can affect the system performance. More specifically, it has been revealed that, for the specific operating conditions examined, in order to have an optimum system performance, an insulation of a total mean thermal resistance R at least equal to $2 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K} \cdot \text{W}^{-1}$ is needed to avoid excess heat losses. In any other case, it has been observed that the heat losses from the sidewalls are considerably high, almost comparable to the heat flux coming out from the emitter Q_{em} (from $Q_{loss}/Q_{em} \approx 6.5 \%$ for $R \approx 2 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K} \cdot \text{W}^{-1}$, up to $Q_{loss}/Q_{em} \approx 65 \%$ for $R \approx 0.1 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K} \cdot \text{W}^{-1}$). In this case, a discrete solid phase is formed near the sidewalls, and a thin crust at the upper part of the PCM, near the PCM-inert gas interface. Due to these formations, there is high risk of entrapping liquid PCM inside the solid PCM that can potentially cause high pressure values inside the crucible. This tendency can be observed in Figure 4a, 30 minutes after the initiation of solidification process. In any other case, i.e. $Q_{loss} \ll Q_{em}$, such formations are not observed, but rather a “crust like” mushy region of the PCM at the sidewalls and the PCM upper part, and only during the final stages of silicon solidification -almost 1 h after the initiation of solidification process (Figure 4b,c and d).

Figure 4. Liquid fraction contours at $t=30, 60$ and 90 min for Cases a) 1A, b) 2A, c) 3A and d) 4A (**Red**: gas-PCM liquid phase, **blue**: PCM solid phase, **dashed black line**: gas-PCM interface).

Finally, the high lateral heat losses, can affect negatively the total power output. This fact is proven in Case 1A, where the power output is lower than in the rest of the cases studied. Therefore, the total heat released during system discharge is considerably lower in Case 1A than in Cases 2A-4A ($Q_{em} \sim 2.3E+03$ kJ in Case 1A, whilst $Q_{em} \sim 3.5E+03$ kJ for the rest of the cases studied). Nevertheless, due to the decreasing temperature difference between the PCM and the environment, as the PCM solidifies, and the increasing values for R as the temperature drops, the heat loss reduces as the time goes by, Figure 5b. Such a fact is more evident for Case 1A, Figure 5b.

Figure 5. a) Solid fraction values and b) heat losses at different time instants for the different insulating layers tested.

During system charge, a proper insulation must ensure quick melting rates, as the ones obtained under adiabatic conditions, since in any other case the excess heat losses from the sidewalls might slow

down the melting process. During this phase, a minor effect on the system heat losses has been observed for values of R equal or higher than $0.1 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K} \cdot \text{W}^{-1}$. The main reason behind that is that in this case the incoming heat from the sidewalls, Q_{wall} , is considerably higher than Q_{loss} , Figure 6b, maintaining the high charging rates that would be achieved under adiabatic conditions, Figure 6a. More specifically, in Case 2A the Q_{wall}/Q_{loss} ratio is almost equal to 10^3 at the beginning of the process and drops down to 10^2 at the end of it. Similarly in Case 1A, the Q_{wall}/Q_{loss} ratio takes values within the range of $10^1 - 10^2$. However, it is expected that for lower Q_{wall} values, comparable to the lateral heat losses, the melting rate will decrease.

Figure 6. a) Melt fraction values and b) heat losses at different time instants for the different insulating layers tested.

3.2. Vessel tapering ratio/ size effect

3.2.1. Charge/ discharge phase

From the analysis, it has been revealed that the system performance during charge/ discharge phase highly depends on key parameters, such as the vessel volume/ storage capacity, tapering ratio and emitter surface. More specifically, for geometries of the same volume (Cases 1B, 4B-6B), the solidification time increases, when their height increases accordingly, since during discharging the dominant direction of heat transfer is the vessel axis, Figure 7a. For this reason, the quickest solidification is observed in Case 6B ($t_{discharge}=0.72 \text{ h}$) and the slowest in Case 5B ($t_{discharge}=2.56 \text{ h}$), which have the lowest and highest height, respectively, of all geometries tested, Table 2. In particular, in Case 6B the solidification time is almost 70 % quicker than in Case 5B. Moderate solidification rates are noticed in Cases 1B and 4B (ITC with a TR=0.45 and 0.225). By comparing these two, it is observed that the ITC with a TR equal to 0.225 (Case 4B) solidifies almost 17 % quicker than that with a TR=0.45.

The opposite trend is expected during the PCM melting period, Figure 7b, since the heat in the specific concept tested comes from the sidewalls. In this case, for the same vessel volume, the higher the height, and therefore the larger the sidewall surface, the quicker the PCM melts. This is the reason why Case 5B -cylinder with a side wall surface equal to 0.044 m^2 , almost 1.3 times bigger than the reference case (Case 1B)- melts quicker than all cases tested. On the other hand, the slowest melting rate can be noticed in Case 6B, where the vessel has the smallest heated wall, equal to 0.0284 m^2 . Concerning the ITC tapering ratio, the vessel with a TR=0.45 melts quicker, due to its bigger surface wall compared to that with a TR=0.225. A trade-off between the system charge and discharge rate leads to the conclusion that the truncated-cone with the tapering ratio, between 0.225-0.45 is the optimum solution to be constructed among the geometries tested.

Concerning lateral losses during charge/ discharge phase, the tapering ratio has a rather not severe effect, when a proper insulation is imposed at the vessel walls. The total amount of losses during the PCM solidification phase are equal to ~ 223 kJ and ~ 158.2 kJ for the truncated-cone with a tapering ratio equal to 0.45 and 0.225, respectively. Such values correspond to a $\sim 3.7\%$ and $\sim 2.6\%$ ratio of the total losses to the initial energy stored (~ 6 MJ) of the system, whilst the $Q_{\text{loss}}/Q_{\text{em}}$ ratio is almost equal to 6.4% and 4.5%, for the two geometries compared. The importance of the insulation should be highlighted, since as aforementioned such losses can be almost an order of magnitude higher, when an insulation of a thermal resistance of an order of magnitude lower than the reference case (Case 2A) is used. During charge period, the same small effect of the TR on the system losses has been noticed – the ratio of $Q_{\text{losses}}/Q_{\text{wall}}$ is less than 1% for all cases studied. Nevertheless, it should be noted that for the same vessel capacity (Case 1B and Cases 4B-6B) and for the specific concept studied, the heat loss decreases with the tapering ratio increasing.

Figure 7. a) Solid fraction and b) melt fraction values for the different geometries tested.

On the other hand, the vessel volume plays an important role on both heat losses and power output. Even though the total system heat losses are almost equal for the three volumes tested during charging, Figure 8b, the total heat losses per stored energy increases with reducing the volume. Specifically, the $Q_{\text{losses}}/E_{\text{in}}$ ratio is equal to 0.1 in Case 1B, whilst in Case 3B ($V'=V/4$, $E_{\text{in}}'=E_{\text{in}}/4$) this ratio is equal to 0.3. For the same cases the total amount of released heat during system discharge is ranges from $-3.5E+03$ kJ for Case 1B (of volume V) to $-9.3E+02$ kJ for Case 3B (of volume $V/4$), Figure 8a.

Figure 8. System heat losses during a) solidification, b) melting for the different geometries tested.

Another conclusion drawn from this analysis is that the possible risk of entrapping of molten PCM inside the solid one, which is related to the imposed insulating method, is not increased when the vessel tapering ratio changes. However, such an observation is valid, as long as an efficient insulating method is imposed at the sidewalls, as abovementioned. Finally, in the case of the shape of truncated cone, a slightly higher expansion can be observed near the PCM centreline than the one noticed near the walls, than in the case of the cylinder, Figure 9.

Figure 9. Comparison of the melt fraction contours at $t=30$ min, after the initiation of discharge phase for: a) Case 1B, b) Case 4B, c) Case 5B, and d) Case 6B.

3.2.2. Storage period

In this section is discussed the potential of the LHTES to store large quantities of energy –in the form of sensible and latent heat- for several days. A key aspect during this period is to identify whether the insulating method imposed is sufficient to eliminate lateral heat losses and keep the PCM temperature close to its melting point, as much as possible. Additionally, different vessel volumes, apart from that of the reference case are investigated, Table 4.

Table 4. Storage time for each vessel (ITC) before it loses its contained latent heat ($t_{\text{discharge, latent}}$).

Case	V_{vessel} [m ³]	A_{vessel} [m ²]	$V_{\text{vessel}}/A_{\text{vessel}}$ [m]	$V_{\text{insulation}}$ [m ³]	$R_{\text{total,1680}}^*$ [m ² K·W ⁻¹]	$t_{\text{discharge, latent}}$ [d]
Case1C	0.0002081	0.02589	0.0080	0.00420	1.18	~0.7
Case2C	0.0004163	0.03344	0.0124	0.00839	1.49	~1.2
Case3C	0.0008326	0.04987	0.0167	0.01678	1.88	~1.8
Case4C	0.0016652	0.07917	0.02103	0.03356	2.37	~2.6
Case5C	0.0033303	0.12567	0.02650	0.06712	2.98	~4.6

Figure 10. a) Temperature variation and b) heat losses per unit mass of the system during TES.

Based on the results, the investigated system can maintain its stored energy in the form of latent heat for almost two days at least partially, Figure 10. However, within one-week storage period the vessel loses considerable amounts of its stored energy and, thus, its temperature drops down to 900 K. Longer-term storage can be achieved, but with vessels of higher capacity, i.e. Case 5C. Added to this it should be noted that the system heat losses per mass decrease with the increasing tank volume. The highest are traced for Cases 1C and 2C; such cases seem impractical for storage even for one day, since they have high lateral heat losses –higher than 200 W/kg- within the first two days of storage.

4. Conclusions

In this work, an extensive analysis has been carried out, by means of an advanced computational fluid dynamics model, to evaluate the performance of a latent heat thermal energy storage system operating at ultra-high temperatures. The storage tank of this system has a volume equal to $V = 8.33 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3$ and contains silicon as a phase change material (PCM). In order to optimize its operation, i.e. eliminate lateral heat losses during charge/ discharge and storage period, maximize power output and achieve high charge/ discharge rates, different insulating materials of a thermal resistance within the range $R = 0.11 - 4.8 \text{ m}^2\text{K/W}$ have been tested. Apart from this, different geometries (truncated cone and cylinder) of different volumes and heights have been tested, as well; in the case of the truncated cone, its height has been modified by altering its tapering ratio (TR) –upper to lower surface ratio. From the numerical analysis it has been revealed that the vessel TR parameter and height have a low to moderate effect on the system heat losses, as long as a sufficient insulation is imposed at the system walls, i.e. of thermal resistance (R) almost equal to $2 \text{ m}^2\cdot\text{K}\cdot\text{W}^{-1}$. Specifically, the total amount of losses during the PCM solidification phase are equal to $\sim 223 \text{ kJ}$ and $\sim 158.2 \text{ kJ}$ for the truncated-cone with a tapering ratio equal to 0.45 and 0.225, respectively. Such values correspond to a $\sim 3.7\%$ and $\sim 2.6\%$ ratio of the total losses to the initial energy stored ($\sim 6 \text{ MJ}$) of the system. During charging, a small effect of the TR on the system losses has been noticed – the ratio of total losses to incoming energy is less than 1% for all cases studied. As regards charge/ discharge rates, an important effect of the TR has been noticed. More specifically, when the tapering ratio of the vessel increases then the solidification, time increases, respectively, whilst the opposite trend is observed during charge phase. A geometry with the same volume, but lower TR (0.225), solidifies quicker than that with $\text{TR} = 0.45$; the solidification time in the first case is almost 17 % lower than in the second case. A trade-off between the system charge and discharge rates leads to the conclusion that the truncated-cone with the TR, between 0.225-0.45 is the optimum solution to be constructed among the geometries tested. Last and foremost, the total energy storage capacity of the tank is significantly influenced by its volume; the specific vessel can be used for storage for up to two days, before it loses its contained energy in the form of latent heat. In summary, building a highly efficient heat storage block aimed to

be integrated in a power-to-heat-to-power system means considering a vessel with short length, low lateral surface area to volume ratio, proper insulating method (of $R \approx 2 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K} \cdot \text{W}^{-1}$) and a tapering ratio, between 0.225-0.45. It should be noticed that the conclusions drawn in this analysis are for the specific designs tested, volume, or volumes close to the one examined and for the specific insulating materials used. For scaled-up geometries, additional runs should be done, to deliver general conclusions, i.e. dimensionless correlations applicable for both large and small-scale systems.

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Nomenclature

b	thickness, m
k	thermal conductivity, $\text{W} \cdot \text{m}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$
Q	heat flux, $\text{W} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$
R	thermal resistance, $\text{m}^2 \text{K} \cdot \text{W}^{-1}$
TR	ratio of upper to bottom vessel surface, [-]

Subscripts and superscripts

abs	absorber
em	emitter
loss	refers to lateral losses, during charge/ discharge and storage period
wall	lateral walls

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